

Influence of 2 forms of N fertilizers, N level, and timing of N application on FS severity in rainfed rice.^a Bajaura, India, 1987 wet season.

Treatments			Severity ^b		
N source	Dose (kg/ha)	Time of application	Smutted panicles (%)	Smutted florets (no./m ²)	
Urea	80	100% after germination	2.61 a (8.75)	19.79 ab (198.0)	
Calcium ammonium nitrate	80	100% after germination	2.39 a (6.07)	9.78 ab (141.6)	
Urea	80	50% after germination, 50% 4 wk after	2.68 a (8.68)	8.73 ab (102.3)	
Calcium ammonium nitrate	80	50% after germination, 50% 4 wk after	2.30 a (5.22)	10.06 ab (166.1)	9.73 (144.58)
Urea	80	35% after germination, 65% 4 wk after	2.60 a (7.20)	11.86 b (195.5)	
Calcium ammonium nitrate	80	35% after germination, 65% 4 wk after	1.86 a (3.00)	7.17 ab (70.8)	
Urea	40	100% after germination	1.92 a (4.08)	5.08 a (35.0)	
Calcium ammonium nitrate	40	100% after germination	1.77 a (3.28)	7.40 ab (77.8)	
Urea	40	50% after germination, 50% 4 wk after	2.10 a (4.06)	7.52 ab (69.5)	6.73 (64.6)
Calcium ammonium nitrate	40	50% after germination, 50% 4 wk after	1.81 a (3.62)	6.94 ab (76.1)	
Urea	25	Farmers' practice (4 wk after germination)	1.78 a (2.69)	4.76 a (28.1)	4.26 (28.1)

^aIn a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other by DMRT (P=0.05). ^bSquare root transformed values. Figures in parentheses are original means.

percentage of smutted panicles.
Analysis of variance results indicate

that both N source and timing
influenced disease severity. □

their location can be determined directly in the field at night.

We released 1,250 marked 1-d-old *N. virescens* adults in late afternoon from a central rice hill to study the effect of host plant resistance on trivial movement of GLH in wetland rice. The fields had been transplanted at 20 × 20 cm with susceptible IR1917 (43 d after transplanting [DT]) and resistant IR29 (31 DT). Although differing by 12 d in age, height and tillering of the two crops were nearly the same.

Sample hills were located in a cruciform design around the source hill, with 2 hills per cardinal direction or 8 hills per distance interval. Marked GLH per hill up to 15 hills from the release center were counted in the evening at 3, 27, 51, and 75 h after release. The number of GLH remaining on the source plant was determined after the last field count.

Leafhopper density in both varieties decreased sharply with increasing distance from the source (see figure). However, the dispersal gradient in resistant IR29 flattened considerably over time compared to that of IR1917.

Dispersal gradients of marked green leafhopper *N. virescens* (Distant) at different times after release in transplanted IR29 and IR1917. IIRI, 1982 wet season.

Insect management

Using fluorescent dye to map dispersal pattern of rice green leafhopper (GLH)

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We developed an efficient technique to mark large numbers of GLH for dispersal studies, using a fluorescent dye with excellent adhering properties and low water solubility. One-day-old, greenhouse-reared *Nephotettix virescens* adults were tagged with dry Saturn Yellow[®] (MF-1) fluorescent powder. As the insects were sucked one by one through a plastic tube (1 m long, 1 cm inner diameter) into the collecting vial of an electrical-powered aspirator, they came in contact with the dye which adhered to the ventral side of their

bodies. About 1,000 insects/h could be processed.

The marked insects were placed on a caged rice plant for recovery. Even after grooming, small specks of dye remained on the coxae, femora, abdominal sterna, ovipositor, and in the margin between the wings and pronotum.

In a replicated greenhouse test, the dye (which is insoluble in water) was retained for at least 10 d and did not affect insect survival.

At night, marked insects illuminated with long-wave UV light glow bright yellow. An inexpensive, portable UV lamp can be made from a standard lantern by replacing the original lamp with a G-W long-wave UV unit (GTE Sylvania[®]). GLH is not attracted to the light emitted.

Recapture of fluorescent-dye-marked insects is not necessary to detect their patterns of movement:

Regression analysis showed that GLH density ($\ln y+1$) was positively related to the inverse of distance in both cultivars. The relationship within time was negative in IR29 but positive in IR1917 (see table). At 75 h after release, 358 (28.6%) marked GLH were counted on the source plant in IR1917; only 20 (1.6%) were counted in IR29.

Leafhoppers tend to make less plant-to-plant movements on

Best-fit regression equations relating GLH density/hill (y) to time after release in hours (x_1) and distance from source in hills (x_2), IRRI, 1982 wet season. Numbers in parentheses are t -values of regression coefficients.^a

Cultivar	Model	df	F value	R ²
IR29	$\ln(y+1) = -0.026 - 0.003x_1 + 1.153(1/x_2)$ (-0.8 ns) (-4.1**) (23.2**)	2,435	276.9**	0.56**
IR1917	$\ln(y+1) = -0.129 + 0.002x_1 + 1.838(1/x_2)$ (-3.7**) (2.4*) (25.3**)	2,451	322.3**	0.59**

^a ns = not significant, * = 0.01 < p < 0.05, ** = p < 0.01

susceptible rice. Antixenosis may stimulate dispersal on resistant rice,

but higher mortality rates may suppress the number of dispersing insects. □

Effect of neem seed and leaf bitters on oviposition and development of green leafhopper (GLH) and brown planthopper (BPH)

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Neem seed bitters (NSB) have shown promise for controlling rice leafhoppers and planthoppers. Neem leaves could also be a source of bitters principals (NLB). We compared the effect of NLB and NSB on oviposition and development of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* and BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* pests.

NLB were extracted from fresh or dried ground leaves; NSB were extracted from crushed kernels using water as a solvent, followed by lyophilization. TN1 rice plants (10 tillers/12-cm-diam pot) were sprayed at 30 d with aqueous solutions of NLB from fresh and from dried leaves and NSB at 500, 2,500, and 5,000 ppm, using an ultralow-volume applicator. Control plants were sprayed with water. The experiment was set up in a randomized complete block design with five replications.

Caged plants were infested with five pairs of newly emerged GLH or BPH males and females. Insects were removed after 5 d and caged plants were kept at $27 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $70 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity for nymph emergence. Nymphs were counted

daily. Plants were dissected and unhatched eggs counted. Total viable and unhatched eggs represented number of eggs laid.

In another trial, roots of 7-d-old TN1 rice seedlings were dipped for 12 h

in 100, 500, or 2,500 ppm solutions of NLB or NSB. Each seedling was transferred to a test tube (1.6 by 12.5 cm) with about 2 ml water and infested with a 1st-instar GLH or BPH nymph. Treatments were replicated 10 times.

Comparison of GLH and BPH eggs laid, eggs hatched, and nymphs that developed to adult stage on rice plants treated with a solution of neem seed bitters (NSB), or bitters from dried (NLBD) or fresh leaves (NLBF), IRRI, 1988. Mean separation at each concentration by DMRT at 5% level. In each box, means at each concentration followed by the same letter are not significantly different.